

Advancements in Device-Free Ultrawide-Band Passive Tracking System

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Abstract—UltraWide-Band low-power devices are one of the most promising solutions for positioning systems, particularly in IoT devices with limited power resources. Analysing changes in the radio spectrum of a static environment, mobile robots or human beings can be detected, allowing for distance computation from the radar devices, typically comprising one transmitter and one receiver. With multiple receivers, a 2D position of the moving object can be determined. This tagless passive tracking system retrieves the trajectory of a moving object without the need for additional electronic devices. The paper presents an IoT positioning architecture achieving a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of about 30 cm.

Index Terms—UltraWide-Band, device-free localisation, sensor-less sensing, multipath-assisted localisation, passive localisation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lately, there has been a growing focus on integrating positioning systems into Internet of Things (IoT) and Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) networks. This surge in interest is mainly attributed to advancements in compact and energy-efficient devices and the large applications fields such as smart farming [1], [2], surveillance [3], [4], building automation [5], traffic telematics [6], structural health monitoring [7], environmental monitoring [8].

Positioning systems classified as *active* [9], [10] are characterised by entities equipped with electronic devices, dubbed as tags, which interact with a deployed network of nodes, known as anchors, to exchange information and estimate their own position [9]–[12]. In contrast, *passive* positioning systems [13] involve entities that either do not possess electronic devices (for instance, in certain healthcare applications [14]–[16] where on-body sensors may not always be practical [17], [18]) or not to exchange information with the anchors. An example illustrating this approach can be found in [19], where the target determines its position by passively listening to messages transmitted from the anchors, resembling the conventional GPS methodology. Among the various Radio-Frequency (RF) technologies available, such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and 5G, Ultra-Wideband (UWB) stands out by surpassing the others due to its well-established and distinct characteristics. Passive positioning systems focus on Device-Free Localization (DFL) systems, where entities without electronic devices are involved [20].

Although camera-based solutions [21], [22] are typical examples, they suffer from computational intensity, high data rates, and privacy concerns due to the need for high-resolution

images. To overcome these limitations, acoustic and ultrasonic systems [23], [24] are often employed to mitigate such drawbacks. However, these systems rely on signals vulnerable to environmental noise interference. Contrarily, RF-based DFL systems have gained prominence by monitoring the target area using measurements of changes in the radio channel spectrum. Specifically, by utilizing UWB radio signals, these systems can measure Channel Impulse Responses (CIRs) to detect and track moving entities [25], [26]. Leveraging the time-domain CIRs provided by UWB modules, it becomes feasible to identify the time locations of MultiPath Components (MPCs) scattered from targets, allowing for accurate estimation of the target’s distance from the baseline of the bistatic radar. This capability facilitates the development of DFL systems on low-cost Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) modules. An early study in this field, presented in [27], constructs an accumulated echogram of a multipath delayed signal. Expanding upon this idea [28], [29] show how CIR measurements can be used to establish a positioning infrastructure, while in [30] a geometrical mapping of the CIRs is implemented to identify reflection sources and determine passenger occupancy.

Building upon [29], the contributions of this paper are threefold: i) A distributed system to detect and track moving entities in the surrounding environment; ii) An IoT architecture to efficiently handle and sort data; iii) A weighting function to enhance the estimation of the time location of MPCs scattered from the target. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section II introduces the algorithm and the weighting function employed to estimate the time location of MultiPath Components (MPCs) scattered from the target. Section III discuss the hardware used in the experiments and presents preliminary results. Finally, Section IV concludes the work with final remarks and potential avenues for improvement.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we provide an overview of the algorithm for estimating the distance of a moving target, either a mobile robot or human being, and propose a filter to estimate the position of the mobile entity. Specifically, Section II-B focuses on a scenario with three UWB transceivers: one transmitter and two receivers, strategically deployed with known coordinates

$$P = [P_1^{TX}, P_2^{RX}, P_3^{RX}] = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 \\ y_1 & y_2 & y_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. In (a): CIR obtained by a single receiver, with MPCs labeled as (τ_0, \dots, τ_n) . Sampling points are indicated by a green circle for received packet 1 and purple rhombus for the successively received packet; in (b): the piecewise parametrization for the variance metric.

A. Channel Impulse Response Reconstruction

The UWB technology employs a sequence of short radio pulses. When receiving the preamble of a packet, the system accumulates the symbols, reconstructing the power envelope of the received signal. The data stored in the accumulator serves two primary purposes: i) Timestamp calculation, ii) CIR reconstruction. The CIR measurements reconstructed by the chosen UWB modules have a resolution of $\Delta\tau_s = 1/(2B_s)$, where $B_s = 499.2$ MHz represents the signal bandwidth. Additionally, it provides an estimation of the time delay of the first path τ_{FP} (i.e., the time delay between transmitter and receiver) within each CIR measurement with a time resolution of $\Delta\tau_s/64 = 1.0016$ ns [31]. The communication channel's temporal behavior is represented by the CIR $h(t) = \sum_{n=0}^N a_n \delta(t - \tau_n)$, where it consists of a series of N shifted, attenuated, and superimposed UWB pulses $\delta(t - \tau_n)$ with amplitude a_n , path delay of the n -th MPC τ_n and $\delta(\cdot)$ denotes the Dirac delta function. The preamble sequences' perfect periodic auto-correlation property enables the receiver to determine the CIR between the transmitter and receiver [27]. As shown in Figure 1-(a), in a stable environment, the complex envelope of the received signal (i.e., $h(t)$) remains constant but is sampled at different time instants [27]. The resulting signal $y(t) = h(t) * s(t) + \varepsilon(t)$, is obtained by the convolution of the CIR $h(t)$ with the input signal $s(t)$ affected by an additive Gaussian white noise process $\varepsilon(t)$, which follows a normal distribution $\varepsilon(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$. Due to this convolution, the resulting signal exhibits features on a scale smaller than a nanosecond, making the sampling period $\Delta\tau_s$ inadequate. As a result, after obtaining the initial CIR measurement, the signal can be discretized into $B = 64$ bins based on the available timestamping resolution. By aligning subsequent CIR measurements relative to the time delay of the first path τ_{FP} , each sample within the CIR can be assigned to the appropriate bin, thereby acquiring B times more samples and achieving a sub-nanosecond scale. The time delay τ_{MPC} of the MPC component associated with the moving target is computed tracking changes in the CIR variance, which is represented as a piecewise constant function (see Figure 1)-(b) with coefficients h_l time-updated as

$$^F h_l^{(k+1)} = ^F h_l^{(k)} + ^F \beta (|Y_i| - ^F h_l^{(k)}), \quad (2)$$

where $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, B-2\}$ is such that $\tau_l \leq \tau_j \leq \tau_{l+1}$, $^F \beta \geq 1$ is a constant scalar sensitivity factor, $|Y_i|$ is the innovation

and the superscripts $^F \cdot$ and $^{(k)}$ stands for the foreground and time instant. The background variation coefficients $^B h_l$ are updated using (2) as well. During the initialization phase, the parameter $^B \beta$ equals $^F \beta$ to expedite the convergence time for building the background model. Once the background model is reconstructed, the parameter $^B \beta$ is adjusted to be much smaller than $^F \beta$.

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$$w(\tau_T) = W \frac{s_i}{s_{max}} \frac{s_{peak}}{s_{max}}. \quad (3)$$

where s_i is the i -th sample of the metric, and its value is normalized by the maximum value of the CIR s_{max} (given by the first path of the background), by the number W of consecutive values of $s_j \geq s_i$ (a larger window size W indicates the existence of multiple unaccounted multipath components generated by the target) and by the ratio between the peak value s_{peak} (occurring when an object enters the scene and creates direct multipath) and s_{max} . The time difference between the time delay of the first path and the time delay of the identified MPC τ_{MPC} , i.e., $\tau_T = \tau_{FP} - \tau_{MPC}$ identifies the target's time of flight.

B. Position Estimation

For each bistatic configuration of the system the target's position P_T is constrained to lie on an ellipse. This ellipse has focal points located at P_1^{TX} and P_i^{RX} , with the major axis equal to $c \tau_T$, and it is described by (4)

$$\|P_i^{RX} - P_T\| + \|P_1^{TX} - P_T\| = c \bar{\tau}_T, \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\tau}_T$ represent the theoretical value of τ_T from the i -th bistatic radar. After obtaining τ_T , there are multiple methods available to estimate the target coordinates $\hat{P}_T = [\hat{x}_T, \hat{y}_T]^T$ [32], [33]. However, this article focuses on enhancing the precision of the raw data, therefore a straightforward particle filter is implemented. Each particle $p = [x_p, y_p]^T$ follows a random walk model. During each prediction step, particle positions are updated with Δt , representing the elapsed time since the last measurement reception. The random variables $\eta_{x_p}(t)$ and $\eta_{y_p}(t)$ represent realizations of a stochastic process, following a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\eta^2)$

$$\begin{cases} x_p^{t+\Delta t} = x_p(t) + \Delta t \eta_{x_p}(t), \\ y_p^{t+\Delta t} = y_p(t) + \Delta t \eta_{y_p}(t). \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Experimental setup

The particles' weights are updated through marginalization $w_p = p(\bar{\tau}_T | \tau_T)$ where the expected $\bar{\tau}_T$ is calculated using (4).

C. Data Sharing Architecture

Sensor data is collected on the onboard computer through the UART interface, facilitating string-based data transfer. In real-time applications, the goal is to minimize the transmitted data size to optimize performance. After decoding all the data, it is transmitted to the central computing unit for additional processing and position estimation. To this end, the Robot Operating System (ROS), an open-source framework that operates on a publish/subscribe protocol, is used as communication layer. The overall architecture is shown in Figure 2 for reference.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The proposed architecture is evaluated using a single TX-RX pair to assess the estimation process of τ_T . A system consisting of three nodes is used to estimate the position of a moving target and to validate the communication layer of the architecture. The experimental area is tracked using both the radar system and the motion capture system provided by Qualisys with 8 Arqus A9 cameras, a synchronisation unit, and a dedicated workstation (see Figure 2).

A. Hardware

The UWB radar node prototype in Figure 3 is built on the Qorvo DWM1001 transceiver. It operates on six frequency bands from 3.5 to 6.5 GHz with bandwidths of 500 or 900 MHz. The chip offers data rates of 110 kbps, 850 kbps, and 6.8 Mbps. The DW1000 timestamp frames with 40-bit precision, resulting in a timing precision of 15.65 ps for packet timestamps. The UWB module connects to a Raspberry Pi Zero v2.0 equipped with a single-core ARM11 processor running at 1 GHz with Ubuntu Server installed. Additionally, two solar panels are incorporated to power the radar node in areas without access to electricity.

B. Results

Figure 4(a) shows the results of an experiment, presenting the derived quantity $c \tau_T$ (i.e., the distance from the baseline) with varying motion speeds from 0.5 m/s to 1.5 m/s. In Figure 4(b), the error histogram points out a mean error $\mu = 30$ mm and a standard deviation $\sigma = 155$ mm. In the previous study [34], we limited the target velocity to be below

Figure 3. In (a) the developed prototype, in (b) the HW architecture.

Figure 4. In (a) comparison between the distance estimated by our approach (blue line) and the distance retrieved by the motion capture (dashed-orange line), in (b) the histogram of the error.

0.15 m/s to accommodate the system's sampling rate and improve tracking precision. The bottleneck in the previous architecture was the UART interface's bandwidth. We optimized the data encoding and fine-tuned the algorithm to address this limitation. As a result, the system can now process and transmit data via ROS at a frequency of 115 Hz, which is four times faster than the previous work that operated at a 30 Hz rate. Figure 5 demonstrates that the weighting function (3) substantially enhances the stability and reliability of target distance estimation in comparison to our previous work [29]. Finally, Figure 6 shows the result of one tracking experiment. After the initial stage of convergence, the estimated position has an $\text{RMSE}(\hat{P}_T)$ of approximately 30 centimetres.

IV. CONCLUSION

Device-Free localization presents significant opportunities for security, logistics, and IoT services. In this study, we improved the leading edge algorithm and introduced a cost function to enhance τ_T estimation. Moreover, we established a comprehensive IoT network and developed a self-powered UWB radar node. These advancements have promising applications and contribute to the progress of device-free localization technology. The system addresses data size concerns and can process data at 110 Hz, achieving an $\text{RMSE}(\hat{P}_T)$ of approximately 30 cm using a straightforward filter. Future research will focus on multi-target tracking and three-dimensional estimation by increasing the number of nodes within the network and using a multi-hypothesis tracking algorithm.

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Figure 5. In (a), the estimated distance using the standard windowing approach adopted in the previous work [29]. In (b) the new approach.

Figure 6. Comparison between target path estimated by UWB and by the MoCap.

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